

THE METHODS OF DETERMINATION IN PUPIL'S UPBRINGING

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Abstract. *Problem of ascertainment in pupils' upbringing is confessed terms of new approach of the teacher's pedagogical skills, the solutions working on theoretically by our pedagogic scientists are highlighted.*

Keywords: *educative technology, diagnose, common method, capability, behavior, inseparableness.*

First of all, it is worth noting that it is difficult to achieve great heights in education without achieving success in education. For this, it is necessary to understand the essence of the concept of "education" of the pupils. Unfortunately, no dictionary provides theoretically a scientific definition of this level directly as a problem. At the same time, in several pedagogical studies, it is emphasized that the social, biological and geographical environment surrounding a person, and the noblest personal characteristics manifested in his(her) interaction with people, determine the upbringing of the educationer. On the basis of determining the "pupil's upbringings" in all educational institutions, unity and continuity are ensured in the educational process, and an opportunity is created to learn the level of formation of the pupil's personal characteristics and qualities, which are implemented in the system of interpersonal relations. Currently, the problem of determining the education of pupils is recognized as one of the new directions of the teacher's pedagogical skill and is a research stage that is theoretically developed by our pedagogic scientists. The definition of education has not been fully reflected in pedagogical scientific literature, which complicates its scientifically based implementation in educational technologies. At the same time, teachers and educators of various categories, such as parents, cannot always give a sufficiently objective assessment of its results. As a result, the education level of pupils of the same character is evaluated differently by wide range of teachers and educators. It is impossible to solve these shortcomings without relying on scientifically-theoretically developed conditions to ensure integrity and continuity in education and upbringing.

Determining whether the student has upbringing education (diagnostics) is a process that determines the level of formation of personal characteristics and qualities of the student, which is carried out by the teacher in the system of interpersonal relations. Based on the analysis of its results, it is possible to improve and enrich the main elements of unity and continuity in educational institutions, and identify and correct deficiencies on time.

The main features of the process of determining the level of "pupil's education" are determined as a result of the use of a system of special methods developed on the basis of the interrelationship of pedagogy and psychology, as well as other disciplines. Pedagogical scientists such as Ya.S.Turbovsky, N.V.Kuzmina, I.P.Rachenko, V.P.Simonov, A.V.Hristeva propose to study the determination of the level of "pupil's education" in three groups:

- wide spread method;
- traditional method;
- diagnostic method.

As a wide spread method, the main laws of dialectics are used - the transition of a person from quantitative changes to qualitative changes, the unity and struggle of opposites, and the laws of negation of negation. Its main feature is that they are used to analyze all phenomena of objective reality, without exception, while providing teachers with accurate information about the studied object, requiring only the last results to be clarified.

Implementation of the traditional method of determining education provides an opportunity to obtain more accurate results. They are already enough developed and used by teachers. As a result of the activities carried out in practice, the observation method is considered acceptable. This method is understood as studying the human feelings of the pupils in their personal activities, their talents in natural (scientific, playful, professional activities, etc.) conditions, and the manifestation of educational characteristics. It envisages the coherence and purposeful aggregation of evidence that describes the actions, behavior, and personal characteristics of the students, which give the opportunity to draw conclusions about the level of education.

The most used method of education is the diagnostic method, in which the activity is conducted as an individual diagnostic interview. This method, from the point of view of pedagogical determination (diagnostics), consists in evaluating the student's level of education on the basis of their coherence and continuity, and analyzing their content. Based on the diagnostic method, the teacher not only deeply understands the inner world of the pupils, their views, beliefs, ideals, and supports their positive aspirations, directs them to solve existing problems, encourages them to do positive actions, provides attention to the elimination of some shortcomings and besides the opportunity to help will have

As the last training method of the general group, the method of analyzing the results of the activity is involved. According to its essence, it consists of upbringing the level of education of the pupil as a result of analysis of the social and other useful labor activities performed in non-educational situations on the basis of ensuring coherence and continuity. This method assumes that the teacher takes into account the actions and interests of the pupils, the high results and shortcomings in the fulfillment of various obligations in the educational process, which is about the characteristics of a particular pupil's career orientation, his(her) character, the degree of formation of his(her) life situation and other activities equally, gives an opportunity to draw a conclusion. In addition to the described methods, a number of other methods for determining the level of education (diagnosis) of the student are described in detail in the pedagogical and psychological literature. Each of them provides for a common goal, based on the analysis of problems related to student education, the teacher will achieve coherence and continuity in educational and educational activities:

the method of document analysis — the content of documents related to the study of the pupil's personality (descriptions, reviews, opinions, etc.);

experimental method - the manifestation of education in specially organized conditions where, according to teachers' opinions, the necessary quality is definitely manifested;

questionnaire method (interview) — the content of the pupil's written or oral answers to the questions asked by the teacher;

- method of independent characteristics — evaluation and discussion of other people's thoughts and opinions about the upbringing of a certain person;

- biographical method - coverage of the period of previous work in the life of a person from a socio-psychological point of view.

Increasing the reliability of the results of determining whether the pupil has been educated (diagnosis) is another condition for achieving high results from the third group of methods. That is, it is recommended to use special private methods. They are often used by professional psychologists in the framework of psychological diagnostics (psychodiagnostics), which is one of the branches of psychology. Currently, more serious attention is being paid to problems related to psychodiagnostics in the education and training system of developed foreign countries. Psychological diagnosis deals with the analysis of the pupil's answers to the questions described in the specially developed questionnaire, and as a result of determining the level of education, it implies the development of a plan of special educational activities for each pupil. Currently, personal questionnaires of foreign psychologists such as G. Eysenck, R. Kettel, Dj. Taylor, Ya. Strelyau adapted to the mentality of each nation and a number of developments of local psychologists are widely spread.

In recent years, survey methodologies have been developed and put into practice with the help of computer technologies. It provides access to the inner world of pupils and expands the possibilities of its use not only by professional psychologists, but also by teachers of various categories. They can also be used in self-diagnosis (reflection). Based on the above-mentioned opinions, teachers and educators-coaches in the educational system of our country should pay attention to the following processes in order to ensure consistency and continuity in their pedagogical activities and achieve high results:

Education is a process of all-round development of a person, formation of his consciousness, behavior and worldview based on a certain, clear goal and socio-historical experience, and not to forget that it has been the basis for determining the content of social relations and organizing them in any system and time.

Education of the young generation is organized based on specific goals in different places and times. A number of tasks are solved in the process of establishing social education. Ensuring that the goals and tasks of education are determined based on the essence of the social system, the level of development, the content of social relations, as well as the worldview, aspirations, dreams and wishes of the citizens of the society.

3. Along with the knowledge of pedagogical skills, the teacher in their professional activities should thoroughly acquire the knowledge of psychological diagnosis, education technology, that is, they should know the individual algorithm of their behavior, the forms of education, and be able to perfectly perform all the operations for the implementation of any education method.

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